

Metal Complexes with *N*¹-Benzoyl-*N*²-(5-phenyl or 5-*p*-anisyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide

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The thiourea derivatives *N*¹-benzoyl-*N*²-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide (BPODTC) and *N*¹-benzoyl-*N*²-(5-*p*-anisyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide (BAODTC) are utilised for the preparation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes in ethanol medium. The structure of the complexes has been studied with the help of analytical and magnetic susceptibility data, uv and ir spectral measurements, conductometric and thermogravimetric analyses. The crystal field parameters of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} are also calculated. BPODTC acts as a bidentate ligand whereas BAODTC a tridentate one, [M₂(BAODTC)₂X₄] and [M(BPODTC)₂X₄], where M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₂⁻ and ClO₄⁻ have octahedral and distorted octahedral configurations, respectively, whereas [Ni₂(BAODTC)₂X₄] is found to be octahedral and [Ni(BPODTC)₂X₄] square planar in nature. Low molar conductance values in acetone except that of [Ni(BPODTC)₂X₄] which is ionic, indicate that all these complexes are non-electrolytic.

METAL complexes with Schiff bases, derived by the condensation of 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole with different aldehydes or ketones, are reported by us earlier¹⁻⁴. Because of biological importance we have also synthesised a number of metal complexes with thiourea derivatives⁵⁻¹¹. A survey of the literature reveals that there is no report on the synthesis of metal complexes with thiourea derivatives having 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole as one of the substituents in the thiourea moiety. In continuation of our studies on metal complexes having fungicidal properties, we report further the synthesis and structural elucidation of a few metal complexes with two thiourea derivatives, *N*¹-benzoyl-*N*²-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide (BPODTC) and *N*¹-benzoyl-*N*²-(5-*p*-anisyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide (BAODTC), which contain C=O, C=S and 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole groups.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. or E.M. grade. The ligands *N*¹-benzoyl-*N*²-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide (pale yellow, m.p. 180°) and *N*¹-benzoyl-*N*²-(5-*p*-anisyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide (canary yellow, m.p. 176°) were synthesised by the reported method^{12,13}. Ethanolic solution of the metal salt and the ligand in proper stoichiometric ratio were refluxed in ethanol for 2-3 h. The coloured precipitates appeared slowly during the reflux which were filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. The complexes were insoluble in water but freshly prepared samples were sparingly soluble in ethanol, acetone, dioxane and benzene. The melting points of the complexes were not sharp and a few decomposed before melting. Based on the

elemental analyses of the complexes by standard methods¹⁴, the composition was proposed. The analytical data, and colour of the complexes are recorded in Table I.

Physical measurements: The electronic spectra of the freshly prepared samples in dioxane and the vibrational spectra (KBr) were recorded on Beckman-35 and Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometers, respectively. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature by Gouy method employing Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as standard. The necessary diamagnetic corrections were made using the literature values¹⁵. Thermal analyses of the complexes were carried out with Netzsch 429 simultaneous thermo analyser at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ by taking 50 mg of the sample in each case. Conductance of the freshly prepared complexes in acetone solutions (10⁻³ M) were measured using a Toshniwal conductance bridge.

Results and Discussion

The ligands BPODTC and BAODTC can exist in different tautomeric intramolecularly hydrogen bonded forms as depicted in Figs. (1-4) (Y=H, OCH₃).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Complex	Colour M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		Sulphur	Nitrogen	Halogen	Metal
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Buff, >250	8.07 (8.17)	14.23 (14.31)	8.99 (9.07)	8.05 (8.13)
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	Yellow, 160 d	7.21 (7.34)	12.64 (12.84)	18.25 (18.35)	7.02 (7.22)
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Buff, >250	7.60 (7.65)	16.73 (16.75)	—	7.51 (7.61)
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Buff, >250	7.21 (7.31)	12.69 (12.79)	8.01 (8.11)	7.07 (7.27)
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Mimosa, 234	6.51 (6.54)	11.47 (11.46)	14.51 (14.52)	12.98 (13.02)
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	Brown, >250	5.54 (5.53)	9.66 (9.69)	27.53 (27.69)	10.99 (11.01)
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Mimosa, >250	5.83 (5.90)	15.47 (15.50)	—	11.69 (11.75)
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Grey, 250	5.11 (5.18)	9.01 (9.08)	11.31 (11.51)	10.22 (10.32)
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Purple, 99 d	8.19 (8.23)	14.32 (14.40)	9.09 (9.13)	7.44 (7.57)
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	Blue, 240	7.40 (7.38)	12.88 (12.92)	18.39 (18.45)	6.72 (6.79)
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Green, >250	7.59 (7.70)	16.73 (16.85)	—	7.11 (7.08)
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Bluish green, 150 d	7.01 (7.06)	12.22 (12.37)	7.75 (7.83)	6.85 (6.50)
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Green, 206	6.82 (6.81)	11.49 (11.57)	14.56 (14.68)	12.08 (12.17)
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	Phiroza, 250 d	5.61 (5.69)	9.71 (9.77)	27.88 (27.92)	10.13 (10.28)
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Red, >250	5.83 (5.96)	15.55 (15.64)	—	10.89 (10.96)
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Leaf brown, 110 d	5.15 (5.28)	9.08 (9.15)	11.51 (11.60)	9.57 (9.62)
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Yellowish green, 237	8.19 (8.24)	14.35 (14.40)	9.11 (9.13)	7.46 (7.55)
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	Yellowish green, >250	7.32 (7.38)	12.69 (12.92)	18.33 (18.46)	6.68 (6.77)
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Canary yellow, 250	7.68 (7.71)	16.79 (16.85)	—	7.00 (7.06)
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Yellowish green, >250	7.12 (7.06)	12.25 (12.37)	7.78 (7.84)	6.86 (6.48)
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Pale yellow, >250	6.59 (6.61)	11.43 (11.53)	14.70 (14.68)	12.05 (12.13)
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	Marine grey, >250	5.60 (5.59)	9.68 (9.78)	27.83 (27.94)	10.12 (10.25)
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Pale yellow, >250	5.89 (5.96)	15.53 (15.66)	—	10.83 (10.94)
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Marine grey, 210 d	5.18 (5.23)	9.07 (9.15)	11.56 (11.61)	9.55 (9.60)

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

The electronic spectra of the ligands show broad bands at $\sim 250 \text{ m}\mu$ (40000 cm^{-1}) and strong broad

bands at $\sim 280 \text{ m}\mu$ (35710 cm^{-1}). These features in uv region are characteristic of longer conjugated systems, thereby causing bathochromic shift and an increase in the intensity of absorption. The ir spectra of the ligands show strong broad bands at $\sim 3400\text{-}3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ probably due to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ vibration. The overlapping of the $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ of the phenyl group, as well as the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ with that of the $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ is clearly indicated by the width of the band¹⁶⁻¹⁷.

A weak band around the region $2600\text{-}2500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu_{\text{S-H}}$ of the thiol group. Again two strong bands observed at ~ 1680 and 1640 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ in ($-\text{CO}-\text{NH}$) systems¹⁷ and conjugated cyclic $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, respectively¹⁸⁻²⁰. The presence of a strong band at $\sim 1180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to the combination mode of $\nu_{\text{NCN+C-S}}$ vibrations.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC TRANSITIONS AND CRYSTAL FIELD PARAMETERS OF Co^{II} COMPLEXES IN cm⁻¹ (EXCEPT β) AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS (μ_{eff})

Complex	⁴ T _{1g} (F)→ ⁴ A _{1g} (F)(ν ₂)	⁴ T _{1g} (F)→ ⁴ T _{1g} (P)(ν ₂)	O.T. band	μ _{eff} B.M.	D _q	B	C	F ₂	F ₄	β
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	15180	17890	—	5.2	881.8	758.1	3503	1268.6	100.1	0.78
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	14930	17860	—	5.0	771.8	811.9	3758	1849.8	107.5	0.89
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	15040	19050	—	5.1	826.0	870	4027	1445.8	115.2	0.89
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	15760	17800	—	5.8	853.1	776.4	3598	1290.4	102.8	0.80
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	15980	18520	28570	4.2	898	828	3814	1868	108.9	0.85
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	15150	17860	27030	4.8	826	787	3440	1808	104.2	0.81
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	15360	18180	26570	4.2	841	809	3711	1832	108.0	0.82
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	15980	17840	28570	4.1	889	763	3584	1268	100.9	0.79

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC TRANSITIONS AND CRYSTAL FIELD PARAMETERS OF Ni^{II} COMPLEXES IN cm⁻¹ (EXCEPT β) AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS (μ_{eff})

Complex	³ A _{1g} (F)→ ³ T _{1g} (F)(ν ₂)	³ A _{1g} (F)→ ³ T _{1g} (P)(ν ₂)	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{1g}	O.T. band	μ _{eff} B.M.	D _q	B	C	F ₂	F ₄	β
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	—	—	22470	27080	Dia	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	—	—	22470	22400	Dia	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	—	—	22470	27400	Dia	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	—	—	22470	27080	Dia	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	16890	27780	—	—	3.2	1084	958	4512	1609	139	0.92
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	16180	27090	—	—	3.1	1025	932	4380	1559	125.8	0.90
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	16180	27070	—	—	2.9	1025	932	4390	1559	165.8	0.90
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	16670	28570	—	—	3.0	1108	1000	4722	1874	184.0	0.96

These observations led to believe that the ligands exist in a tautomeric equilibrium. Apart from these, a number of bands also appear at ~1580, 1505, 1030 and 910 cm⁻¹. The former two bands are assigned to phenyl ring ν_{C=C} skeletal vibrations⁹, whereas the later two bands are due to ν_{C-O-C=} and ν_{N-N} vibrations of the oxadiazole ring²¹⁻²⁴. The low frequency bands at ~840 and 750 cm⁻¹ are assigned to aromatic *para*-disubstituted δ_{C-H} vibration and the band at 710 cm⁻¹ to ν_{C=S} mode¹⁶.

The ν_{N-H} and ν_{C-O-C=} bands observed in the spectra of the ligands in the regions 3400-3200 and 1030 cm⁻¹ remain unaffected in the spectra of the metal complexes indicating the non-coordination of the NH groups and the oxygen atom of the oxadiazole ring. But significant change is observed in the bands at ~1680, and 1180 cm⁻¹. In all the metal complexes these bands are shifted to lower frequency by 20-30 cm⁻¹ suggesting the coordination of the carbonyl oxygen and thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms to the metal ion¹⁶. The band at ~1260 cm⁻¹ (C-N) of the ligand is shifted to higher frequency region by 5-10 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the metal complexes.

The ir band at 910 cm⁻¹ (N-N)²⁵ of the ligands (N-N) decreases in intensity and is shifted to higher frequency by 5-10 cm⁻¹ in all the binuclear complexes of the type, [M₂(BAODTC)₂X₄] due to π electron interaction of the oxadiazole ring of the ligand with the metal ion. This is further confirmed by bathochromic shift of the ligand band at 1640 cm⁻¹ characteristic of cyclic conjugated C=N vibration due to delocalisation of the π electron over the oxadiazole moiety on complexation. This indicates that the ring nitrogen also takes part in coordination. These bands remain unaltered in the complexes of the type [M(BPODTC)₂X₂] and

[M(BPODTC)₂]X₂ suggesting non-coordination of oxadiazole ring nitrogen in these mononuclear complexes.

In the spectra of perchlorato complexes, the ir bands of the perchlorato group due to ν_{C-O} is split into three components appearing at 1130, 1115 and 1095 cm⁻¹. The extent of splitting indicates the presence of coordinated perchlorato group²⁴⁻²⁶. Coordination of the nitrate ion to the metal ion in the nitrate complexes is established by the appearance of strong additional bands at ~1390 and 1315 cm⁻¹ which are the split components of ν₂ characteristic of monodentate nitrate ion²²⁻²⁴. But the absence of these bands in the nitrate and perchlorato Ni^{II} complexes with ligand BPODTC is conspicuous, indicating the counter-ions to be outside the coordination sphere.

Magnetic properties and electronic spectra: The electronic transitions, magnetic moments, etc. of the complexes are recorded in Tables 2-4.

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC TRANSITIONS IN cm⁻¹ AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS (μ_{eff}) FOR Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Complex	² E _g → ² T _{2g}	O.T. band	μ _{eff} B.M.
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	14810	27080	1.8
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	14980	27780	1.9
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	14710	27400	1.9
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	14810	27080	1.7
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	13330	27080	0.806
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	13700	27080	1.42
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	14490	27400	1.65
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	14290	27080	1.15

TABLE 5—THERMAL STABILITY OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Temp. °C		% weight of residue Found (Calcd.)
	Commencement of decomposition	Completion of decomposition	
[Cu(BPODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	230	580	9.35 (9.12)
[Co(BPODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	190	580	10.92 (10.44)
[Ni(BPODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	160	300	9.51 (9.60)
[Cu ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Cl ₂]	220	700	16.33 (16.28)
[Co ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ Br ₂]	250	680	14.42 (13.98)
[Ni ₂ (BAODTC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	220	400	12.58 (12.62)

The Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with the ligand BAODTC are presumed to be octahedral or distorted octahedral as indicated from the band position in the electronic spectra. The sub-normal magnetic moments in these binuclear complexes are due to spin-spin interaction of the metal centres through the symmetrically bridged sulphur atom, resulting in the partial quenching of the paramagnetism. This observation further supports the view that, in case of the ligand BAODTC, the presence of a *para*-methoxy group in the phenyl ring enriches the electron density on the oxadiazole ring-nitrogen due to resonance and hence the ring nitrogen also acts as a coordinating site (Fig. 5). The Cu^{II} and Co^{II} complexes with ligand BPODTC are suggested to be octahedral in nature as indicated

Fig. 5

M = Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}.X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻.

from the electronic spectra and magnetic moment values. However, the electronic spectra of the complexes of the type [Ni(BPODTC)₂]_nX_n reveal them to be square planar in nature. The diamagnetic nature of these complexes support the above view.

The crystal field parameters calculated from the transitions observed in the electronic spectra of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes (Tables 2 and 3) are in agreement with the earlier reports^{21,22}. The β values in the octahedral complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} are less than unity indicating partial covalency in the metal ligand bond.

The molar conductance values of all the complexes is low (12-20 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicating their

non-electrolytic nature except [Ni(BPODTC)₂]_nX_n which is found to be ionic with λ_M values in the range 120-130 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$.

Thermal analysis: The complexes are highly stable at room temperature and most of the complexes decompose only after 200°. No complex gives endothermic peak upto 200° which indicates the absence of either lattice water or water of crystallisation as well as the coordinated water molecules in the complexes. As seen from the thermograms, the decomposition of the complexes start around 200° indicated by exothermic peaks. On the basis of mass loss, the final residue obtained in air corresponds to the oxides of divalent metals of copper and nickel, whereas Co₃O₄ is found for the Co^{II} complexes. This is confirmed by small gain in mass in the TG curves for Co^{II} complexes at higher temperature (~600°) and is perhaps due to the oxidation of the metal from the lower valent state to the higher oxide. The endothermicity after 200° is due to the decomposition of organic ligands followed by exothermic peaks due to the oxidation of the organic products. The perchlorate complexes undergo sudden decomposition with explosion ~230° as indicated by sharp exothermic peaks in the TG curves at the same temperature. Thermal data of a few of the complexes are recorded in Table 5. A study of the decomposition pattern and the nature of the thermograms confirm to the stoichiometry suggested for the complexes.

References

1. K. O. SATPATHY, R. MISHRA and B. B. JAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 340
2. K. O. SATPATHY, R. MISHRA and B. B. JAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 618.
3. K. O. SATPATHY, R. MISHRA and B. B. JAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, in the press.
4. K. O. SATPATHY, B. B. JAL and R. MISHRA, *Trans Met. Chem.*, in the press.
5. K. O. SATPATHY, T. D. MAHANA and H. P. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 56, 248.
6. K. O. SATPATHY, H. P. MISHRA, A. K. PANDA, A. K. KABISATPATHY and A. TRIPATHY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 761.

7. K C SATPATHY and H. P. MISHRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 1086
8. K C SATPATHY and H P MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 844
9. K C. SATPATHY, H. P. MISHRA and B. N. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 40
10. K C SATPATHY, H. P. MISHRA and G. O. PRADHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 612
11. K. C. SATPATHY, H. P. MISHRA and B N. PATHL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 898.
12. F L SCOTT, T M LAMBA and R N BUTLER, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1972, 1918.
13. R. E. LAUER and G. ZENCKEL, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 292.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 8rd ed., E. L. B S. and Longmans, London, 1969.
15. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS in "Modern Coordination Chemistry", eds. J. LEWIS and B. G. WILKINS, Interscience, New York, 1960, p. 416.
16. J R DYER, "Application of Absorption Spectroscopy to Organic Compounds", Prentice-Hall, Englewood-Cliffs, 1965, p. 84.
17. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1968, p. 225.
18. K C SATPATHY, H P. MISHRA and R. MISHRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **47**, 276.
19. B. DAS, and S K. MAHAJATRA, *J. Inorg Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 27
20. B. S. SHARMA and S. O. BAMEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 877
21. B. G SAHA, B P. BHATNAGAR and S K. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 927.
22. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1966, p. 350
23. N. B SINGH and J. SINGH, *J. Inorg Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 919
24. I. K. VERMA and O K. GENTHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 352.
25. B. J. HATHWAY and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 8091.
26. N. SAHA and K. M. DATTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 728.
27. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, London, 1968, p. 365.
28. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 245.